

COVID-19 EHS-EKA Survey

Thank you for participating in this survey.

We would like to ask you to kindly take approximately 8 minutes of your time and complete an online survey regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and how it affects your patients and your practice.

All data and questions will be absolutely anonymous. All answered questions will be saved so that you will be able to return to your latest question and go on with the survey from that question.

1. In which country are you currently working?

Country

2. What is your orthopedic speciality? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - adult hip reconstruction | <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - sports-medicine |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - adult knee reconstruction | <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - pediatrics |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - spine | <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - traumatology |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - foot and ankle | <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - general |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - musculoskeletal oncology | <input type="checkbox"/> Resident/ Fellow - not specified yet |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedics - shoulder and elbow | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above or other (please specify) | |

3. In which type of environment are you working? (Mark all that apply)

- Academic medical center
- Public hospital
- Private hospital

4. How many years have you been practicing?

5. Do you fear infecting your friends or family and what is your approach for prevention? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I don't go home anymore (stay at the hospital, hotel, second apartment, etc.) | <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I wear a surgical mask/other protection at home |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I wash and disinfect my hands more often than usual | <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I avoid close physical contact with my family members |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I change my clothes in the hospital more often | <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I am more careful at work than usual |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I try to keep a distance to my family at home | <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I took off from work |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I don't stay in the same room with other members of my family anymore | <input type="checkbox"/> No, I don't care at all |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I disinfect surfaces in my home after I touch them | <input type="checkbox"/> No, I haven't thought about this situation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

6. What specific effects has the COVID-19 pandemic had on your department?(Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No changes at the department | <input type="checkbox"/> The department has stopped elective outpatient surgery |
| <input type="checkbox"/> All surgeries have been stopped | <input type="checkbox"/> The hospital has selectively restricted inpatient elective surgery |
| <input type="checkbox"/> The department has stopped elective inpatient surgery | <input type="checkbox"/> The hospital has selectively restricted outpatient elective surgery |

7. What specific effect has the COVID-19 pandemic had on your outpatient clinic?

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="radio"/> ALL patients are being tested for SARS-CoV-2 prior to orthopedic clinical examination | <input type="radio"/> No changes at our outpatient clinic |
| <input type="radio"/> ALL patients are being screened for SARS-CoV-2 (e.g. having body temperature taken, answering a questionnaire, etc.) prior to orthopedic clinical examination | <input type="radio"/> Only patients with acute orthopedic symptoms (fracture, infection, tumor eg. bone sarcoma) are allowed at our outpatient clinic |
| <input type="radio"/> Patients with positive symptoms/positive screening questions are being tested for SARS-CoV-2 | |
| <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify) | |

8. How has the COVID-19 pandemic affected YOUR practice as an orthopedic surgeon? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No impact | <input type="checkbox"/> More non-surgical orthopedic clinical care is being performed |
| <input type="checkbox"/> My volume of performed surgery is reduced | <input type="checkbox"/> More administrative work is being done |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Discussing the delay due to the pandemic with patients | <input type="checkbox"/> Orthopedic surgeons are assigned more often to non-orthopedic patient care due to the pandemic |
| <input type="checkbox"/> No Training or teaching (students, residents, fellows) due to the pandemic | |

9. Are the following procedures currently being performed currently being performed at your department?

	yes	stopped	delayed	not provided at our department
"elective" Primary total joint arthroplasty (TJA)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
First stage explantations for <i>acute</i> PJI (periprosthetic joint infection)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
First stage explantations for <i>chronic</i> PJI (periprosthetic joint infection)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Second stage reimplantations for PJI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
One stage revisions for <i>acute</i> PJI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
One stage revisions for <i>chronic</i> PJI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Aseptic TJA revisions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Massively failedTJA (collapse, dislocation,component failure, imminent dislocation)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Periprosthetic fracture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TJA for rapid progressive osteoarthritis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conversion from osteosynthesis to PJA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
THA/hemi-arthroplasty for femoral neckfractures	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Amputation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
TJA reconstruction after bone sarcoma resection	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. Imagine 4 Stages of escalating down activities, in *which stage* is your department department *at this time*?

- Stage 1*: first cancellations (primary joint arthroplasties, elective inpatient/outpatient surgeries)
- Stage 2*: secondary cancellations (avascular femoral head necrosis, semi-acute revision surgeries)
- Stage 3*: last to be cancelled (e.g. high risk bone sarcoma)
- Stage 4*: emergency cases only (patients in acute life threatening conditions e.g.periprosthetic fractures/infections)

11. Has there been any specific COVID-19 training for your surgical staff?

- yes
- no

12. Has there been a positive COVID-19 test result (infection proved)? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Patient in my hospital | <input type="checkbox"/> Other staff in my hospital |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Patient in my department | <input type="checkbox"/> Other staff in my department |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Health care professional in my hospital | <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Health care professional in my department | |

13. Have there been any disruptions related to the pandemic? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Staff disruptions | <input type="checkbox"/> Missing regular inpatient beds |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Supply disruptions | <input type="checkbox"/> Missing COVID-19 intensive care units |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Missing regular intensive care units | <input type="checkbox"/> Missing COVID-19 intermediate care units |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Missing regular intermediate care units | <input type="checkbox"/> Missing COVID-19 inpatient beds |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |
- _____

14. With regard to your regular meetings, is there any difference due to the COVID-19 pandemic?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> No difference at my department | <input type="radio"/> ALL staff members participate at the meetings but keep a distance to each other |
| <input type="radio"/> Reduced staff at the meetings | <input type="radio"/> ALL staff members participate at the meetings but wear protection (masks, coats etc.) |
| <input type="radio"/> No meetings anymore | <input type="radio"/> Meetings are held exclusively online via videoconference |
| <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify) | |
- _____

15. What are your clinic's approaches to preventing sick leave due to COVID-19 pandemic? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Staff is separated into groups | <input type="checkbox"/> Personal protection (masks, coats, gloves etc.) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced staff appearance at meetings | <input type="checkbox"/> Remote working from home (scientific research, webinars, telemedicine etc.) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Altered rotations in staff appearance | <input type="checkbox"/> No prevention |

16. Do you offer patient care via technologies like telemedicine? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Videoconference (Skype, Zoom, etc.) | <input type="checkbox"/> Telephone |
| <input type="checkbox"/> web based telemedicine (FaceTime, GoogleChat etc.) | <input type="checkbox"/> EHR/EMR (electronic healthrecord/
electronic medical record) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> None | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

17. How long do you think the COVID-19 pandemic will affect your clinical routine/your surgical schedule?

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input type="radio"/> 2 to 4 weeks | <input type="radio"/> 6 to 9 months |
| <input type="radio"/> 5 to 8 weeks | <input type="radio"/> 9 to 12 months |
| <input type="radio"/> 9 to 12 weeks | <input type="radio"/> more than 12 months |
| <input type="radio"/> 3 to 6 months | |

18. What impact has the COVID-19 pandemic had on you? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> I am effectively not involved in any surgical activity due to institutional or self-imposed deferral of elective surgery | <input type="checkbox"/> At this time, no confirmed cases of COVID-19 have occurred in my community or institution |
| <input type="checkbox"/> I am not working due to personal illness, COVID-19 exposure, or post-travel quarantine | <input type="checkbox"/> Confirmed COVID-19 cases have occurred in my community or institution |
| <input type="checkbox"/> I consider myself in a high-risk group for COVID-19 (age > 60, underlying condition e.g. high blood pressure, diabetes, cardiovascular disease) | <input type="checkbox"/> None |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

19. Do you still perform follow up investigations on TJA patients? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, clinical follow up | <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, but I follow up only high risk patients (e.g. complex revisions, septic, etc.) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, radiological follow up | <input type="checkbox"/> No, the sutures are taken out by someone else (e.g. general physician/family doctor) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I take the sutures out myself | <input type="checkbox"/> No, the patients are not followed up anymore |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

20. Is any physical therapy or rehabilitation offered for already discharged TJA patients? (Mark all that apply)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, inpatient | <input type="checkbox"/> No |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, outpatient | <input type="checkbox"/> Only for selected cases |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |
